

The Effects of Job involvement and Professional Commitment on Organizational Citizenship Behaviour: (A conceptual framework).

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Abstract

Business today has become so competitive that most organizations strive to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of their employees so that they can achieve excellence. . One of the ways through which these organizations can achieve this is through the behaviors of their employees. It has been noted by several researchers that organizational citizenship behavior is a workplace behavior, which is optional because when individuals engage in this kind of behavior they voluntarily do more than is, expected of them for the organization and this in turn increases their performance as well as that of the entire organization. It has been mentioned by many researchers that job involvement and professional commitment support are two factors that can significantly affect the sustainability of organizations as well as the organizational citizenship behavior while increasing the competitive advantage of the organization. Based on the fact organizations strive to support their employees as well as strengthen their commitment. In general, findings of past studies have argued that organizational citizenship behaviour is directly determined by job involvement and professional commitment. By highlighting the effects of job involvement and professional commitment on the organizational citizenship behaviour, the direct and indirect effects on employee performance are explained in this article.

Keywords: Job involvement, Professional Commitment, Organizational Citizenship Behaviour.

1. Introduction

Motivating and managing employees in an organization remains one of the major challenges faced by leaders in a highly competitive world. Thus, for the competitive advantage of an organization to be sustained, the effective management of human resources alongside their attitudes is crucial (Ibrahim, Ghani, & Embat, 2013). In this regard, job attitude is being considered by Judge and Kammeyer-Mueller (2012) as a crucial and central aspect of employee behaviour. They argue that job attitudes are very important because they have the potentials of predicting important behaviour. According to Judge and Robbins (2015), the potential advantages of employee attitude and behaviours to the individual and the organization are the driving force for the increasing interest in organizational topics related with behaviour and attitude. Hettiararchchi and Jayarathna (2014), posit that the concepts work attitude have become popular because of its relationship with different employee behaviours. Thus, an employee that is satisfied and committed is less likely to exhibit poor performance because he/she is usually highly productive as they identify with values and goals of the organization (Hettiararchchi & Jayarathna, 2014).

Basically, it is important to note that the attitudes of human resources to their work is very important and that there are so many challenges associated to these attitudes including the inability of management to deal with such work related attitudes and how they affect the behaviour and performance of employees (Emami, Alizadeh, Nazari, & Darvishi, 2012). More so, Jain et al., (2011) approve that other fields of study such as the relationship between work-related attitude and organizational citizenship behaviour can benefit from the increasing interest in organizational citizenship behavior (OCB).

Job involvement reflects the degree that employee is cognitively engaged in, preoccupied with and concerned with his/her current job (Zhang, 2014). Many researchers emphasized that employees' involvement in work processes can influence organizational and individual outcomes like organizational citizenship behaviour (Feldt, Hyvönen, Oja-Lipasti, Kinnunen, & Salmela-Aro, 2012). Even though it has been found that OCB is strongly influenced by job involvement, studies on the relationship between job involvement and organizational citizenship behavior is scanty (Chughtai, 2008; Zhang, 2014). Findings of previous studies have shown that

organizational citizenship behaviour can be predicted by appropriate job involvement rather than role-required tasks (Somers and Birnbaum, 1998). A review of the existing literature shows that few studies that have been conducted to examine the relationship between job involvement and organizational citizenship behaviour found a positive relationship between the two variables (Chughtai, 2008; Cohen, 2006; Rotenberry & Moberg, 2007).

Professional commitment is another concept which is parallel to the concept of organizational commitment as well as the manner in which ones attitude towards his/her organization may be affected by ones professional attitude (Özdem, 2012). This implies that individuals may not be committed to their organization even if they are committed to their work (Ceylan & Bayram, 2006). It has been revealed that individuals are more willing to maintain their professional membership and go beyond the boundaries in their profession while strongly identifying with their professional goals, if they have high level of professional commitment (Chang et al., 2015).

Kannan & Pillai, (2008) confirmed that the work behavior of people could be determined by professional commitment. It has also been found that professional commitment is correlated with organizational and professional outcomes like reduced turnover, work performance and job satisfaction (Elias, 2006). Thus, individuals whose level of professional commitment is high, tend to engage more in activities that are of benefit to the organizations; this finding has been validated in a study which was carried out in health organizations (Caricati et al., 2014)

Researchers emphasized the importance of job involvement and professional commitment in the relationship between organization and employees; the manner in which work attitude and employee behaviours is affected by the relationship between employees and organization is explained using the social exchange theory. This theory provides an explanation for the mutual exchange relationships agreed upon by different parties such as employer and employee (Cook, Cheshire, Rice, & Nakagawa, 2013). The postulates that parties go into exchange relationships expecting to be rewarded while maintaining the relationship (Melián-González, 2016). According to Miles (2012) since in social exchange theory, each party possesses something valuable, which the other needs, both parties reach an agreement on what to exchange and in what quantities. However, inequalities in the employment relationship can be caused by negative imbalance in the relationship. Therefore, employees feel happy and appreciated when they are rewarded by their organizations. This makes them to give more support to their organization, feel satisfied with their jobs, and exhibit positive attitudes and behaviours.

Extra-role behaviours and in-role behaviours are the two main classifications of individual behaviours. Extra-role behaviours include behaviours like helping new colleagues, rendering assistance to colleagues with much work and promoting the organization (Dash & Pradhan, 2013). Researchers have defined organizational citizenship behaviour as behaviours that are voluntarily exhibited by employees; the performance of the individuals and that of the organization can be improved through this optional behaviour (Dash & Pradhan, 2013; Kevin, 2016; Rose, Miller, & Kacirek, 2016). Organizational citizenship behaviour can affect individual performances in negative and positive ways (Dash & Pradhan, 2013). More so, the overall performance of the organization can be impacted by organizational citizenship behaviour which influences individual behaviours (Coldwell & Callaghan, 2014; Jain, Giga, & Cooper, 2011; Van Dooren, Bouckaert, & Halligan, 2015). Some researchers have argued that the theoretical and practical aspect of organizational citizenship behaviour can provide insight on the significance of social connections within societies (Bergeron, Ostroff, Schroeder, Block, 2014; Rose, 2016).

1. Theoretical Background

1.1 Job Involvement and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

The degree to which an individual identifies psychologically with his/her work, or the importance, which he/she attaches to the job, is a reflection of job involvement (Zhang, 2014). Through employee involvement, the

autonomy of employees at workplace increases and they are able to participate in decision making and problem-solving (Willard, 2012). Due to this autonomy and empowerment of employees, it is expected that employees will be more committed, motivated, productive and satisfied with their work. Based on the outcome of employee involvement, contemporary management has made it a basic practice to allow their employees participate in decision-making process, gain sharing and quality circles (Willard, 2012).

Tatlah, Ali & Saeed (2011), argue that when employee involvement is encouraged by organizations, there will be a downward movement of decision-making power within the organization, which leads to accountability and authority sharing in the organization. Concurrently, job involvement is regarded as a major factor which influences significant organizational and individual outcomes (Zhang, 2014). High level of involvement is a response to emotional need rather than rational need, because through job involvement employees become emotionally attached to an organization. For instance, a managerial position is very tasking, so managers often remain at work after normal working hours to get things done; this implies extreme involvement (Permarupan, Al-Mamun, & Saufi, 2013). A conclusion was made by Sofijanovna and Zabijakin-Chatleska (2013) that, there is a positive correlation between effective use of employee involvement and perceived organizational performance. In the literature, job involvement has positive organizational impacts as it influences the extent to which an employee supports the goals of the organization, thereby leading to an increase in efficiency and productivity (Brown & Leigh, 1996).

Chu et al., (2005) who carried out a study in one of Taiwan's health care institutions which is a non-western location, found that the organizational citizenship behavior of hospital nurses was influenced by antecedents such as social support, job satisfaction, procedural justices and job involvement. An understanding of the cross-cultural dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior can be enhanced through the finding of this study since it was carried out in a non-Western site in one of Taiwan's health care institutions.

Rotenberry and Moberg (2007) posits that both forms of organizational citizenship behavior are predicted by job involvement. Findings of the study conducted by Chughtai (2008) supports this position as it revealed the there is a positive relationship between both in-role job performance and organizational citizenship behavior. However, Paillé (2010) who studied organizational citizenship behavior in workplace by examining work attitudes as organizational citizenship behavior predictors among French employees, found that organizational citizenship behavior is negatively impacted by job involvement. A study which was recently carried out by Zhang (2014), examined the correlation between job involvement and the five dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior among a group of people in the Republic of China. The findings indicated that there is a positive relationship between job involvement and all the dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior.

1.2 Professional Commitment and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

Professional commitment as defined by Morrow and Wirth (1989) is the psychological attachment and identification with one's profession. It has been revealed that individuals are more willing to maintain their professional membership, and go beyond the boundaries in their profession while strongly identifying with their professional goals, if they have high level of professional commitment (Chang et al., 2015). It is clear that, the concept of professional commitment is related to professional identity, being patriotic to the profession, being committed to the values, objectives, norms and ethics of the profession (Sharma, Bisht, & Chopra, 2013). In recent times, the focus on professionalism has been emphasized due to the increase in technology and knowledge which has resulted into the movement toward workplace specialization. This has also resulted in the increase of the number of professionals and specialists (Singh & B. Gupta, 2015).

The study which was carried out by Özdem (2012), showed that organizational commitment, professional commitment and OCB are positively correlated, while professional commitment being more related to OCB. It was further found in the study that, 26% of the variance of OCB perceptions among teachers, was attributed to professional and organizational commitment. In professional and organizational commitments alone were

determined to explain the OCB perceptions of the teachers at the rate of 33% and 9%, respectively. This means that the teachers demonstrated higher level of professional commitment than organizational commitment.

Cohen and Kol (2004) showed that professionalism, and in particular when the dimension profession is used as referent, is a predictor of altruism and compliance dimensions of OCB. A recent study done by Duarte (2015) showed how organizational commitment and professional commitment are related with nurses' OCB. Data from a sample of 420 nurses working in two hospitals were collected. The main findings are as follows: (a) organizational commitment and professional commitment contribute to the explanation of nurses' OCB, (b) affective professional commitment, affective organizational commitment; personal sacrifice, continuance organizational commitment, and continuance professional commitment explain 28.6% of variance of OCB.

2. Model Development

According to Baran, Shanock & Miller (2012), it is of great importance to study the factors that determine the relationship between employees and the organization which makes the employees feel committed to their organization (Baran, Shanock, & Miller, 2012). A review of literature has revealed the existence of little of findings on the effect of job involvement on organizational citizenship behaviour. Zhang (2014) claimed that a few studies that have examined the relationship between job involvement and organizational citizenship behaviour showed that there is a positive relationship between job involvement and organizational citizenship behaviour (Chughtai, 2008; Rotenberry & Moberg, 2007). For instance, Munene (1995) found a positive relationship between job involvement and conscientiousness component of supervisor-rated organizational citizenship behaviour. Meanwhile, Somers and Birnbaum (1998) found a weak but significant correlation between job involvement and organizational citizenship behaviour.

In addition, previous studies have found a correlation between professional commitment and improved attention, client service. Job involvement and technical performance (Anderson, Hair, & Toderro, 2012; Duffy, Dik, & Steger, 2011; Kim & Brymer, 2011). The findings of a study carried out by Özdem (2012) revealed that compared to organizational commitment, professional commitment is more correlated with organizational citizenship behavior. Despite this finding, just little attention has been given to the relationship between professional commitment and organizational citizenship behaviour with much negligence coming from the trending paradigm in the literature of management in relation to the correlation between professional commitment and organizational citizenship behaviour (Duarte, 2015; Özdem, 2012). Therefore, this study is carried out to examine job involvement and professional commitment as a determining factor of organizational citizenship behaviour based on the recommendations of other researchers and inadequate specific studies. By examining the effect of job involvement and professional commitment on organizational citizenship behaviour, this study seeks to identify and bridge the possible gaps that might have a consequence on the current study.

Figure 1.1: Job Involvement and Professional Commitment as determinants of OCB.

3. Conclusion

Based on the review of literature on job involvement, professional commitment as determinants of organizational citizenship behaviour there are scares of studies regarding the effect of job involvement and professional commitment on citizenship behaviour. The current literature highlights job involvement and professional commitment as factors that significantly influence organizational citizenship behaviour.

Previous results for (Chu et al. 2005; Chughtai, 2008; Zhang, 2014) studies confirmed that greater job involvement would generate a higher OCB. This indicates that employee involvement motivates and empowers employees to make their contribution to individual and organizational performance. In other words, employee involvement gives employees autonomy at workplace, which lets them participate in decision-making, problem solving and extra role behavior (Willard, 2012). More so, a high level of involvement is a response to emotional need rather than rational need, because through job involvement employees become emotionally attached to an organization (Permarupan, Al-Mamun, & Saufi, 2013).

On the other hand, researchers found a significant positive effect of professional commitment on organizational citizenship behavior (Caricati et al., 2014; Kannan & Pillai, 2008; Özdem, 2012). In addition, when employee committed to their profession they are more willing to display organizational citizenship behavior. For example, Duarte (2015) revealed that the development of nursing profession could be enhanced through the provision of the Code of Practice for Portuguese Nurses and the Code of Ethics for Nurses, which states the principles of this profession. Through these normative tools, nurses are able to help their colleagues while maintaining a high standard personal conduct for the dignity of the profession. Such behaviours can be regarded as the behaviour, which is referred to as organizational citizenship behaviour in the literature. Furthermore, previous study has found that there is a correlation between professional commitment and organizational and professional outcomes such as work performance (Elias, 2006).

As a result of the rapid global change, organizations are working hard to learn as well as teach their employees organizational behaviour that will help the organization adapt and thrive successfully in the global competitive marketplace which is continually changing. In this regard, it is expected that employees go beyond their roles, job descriptions and duties to enhance the overall performance of the organization. Managers of organizations are in need of such employees who can go beyond their job boundaries to ensure that the performance of the organization is excellent. This kind of behaviour displayed by employees also gives room for the development of organizational citizenship behaviour. In addition to that, understanding the principle of reciprocity guarantees the reciprocation of benefit by the other party (Yadav & Rangnekar, 2014). Hence, Settoon et al. (1996) argued that it is based on exchange relationships that employees benefit from support and resources. Similarly, organizations benefit from behaviours and attitudes of employee related to quality workplace exchanges. Therefore, this model examined this reciprocity relationship and found that individuals are driven by the principles of social exchange theory to demonstrate organizational citizenship behaviour even without being assured of any formal reward from the other party. It can therefore be concluded that this study contributes to the literature on job involvement, professional commitment and organizational citizenship behaviour. This study indicates that job involvement, professional commitment are major determinants of citizenship behaviours. Thus, organizations should give priority to employee involvement as well as enhance their professional commitment, which will in turn motivate them to be willing to perform extra roles outside their job descriptions in order to achieve the goals of the organization.

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